

Traditional Healing Practices and Perspectives of Mental Health in Nagaland

Longkumer Ningsangrenla and PSS Rao

In-depth interviews on representative random cluster samples of 510 rural and 300 urban households were done during 2017 to assess traditional healing practices for mental health in Nagaland. Three main modalities of traditional treatments - herbal, mechanical and psycho-spiritual were used either singly or in combination. Nearly 30% consulted a traditional healer, 34.8% in the rural and 16.5% in the urban. 58.9% reported that the outcome was good. 60% in the rural but only 24% in the urban felt that traditional healers are still popular for mental health as they are competent and adopt culturally acceptable methods. It is concluded that for a majority of people in Nagaland, traditional methods of healing mental disorders still remain the first point of contact. While traditional healers are still popular, their number is decreasing and also their capacity to deal with increasing substance abuse, stress disorders and younger clientele.

Keywords: Mental Health, Traditional Healing, Nagaland, Practices, Perspectives

Introduction

A comprehensive mental health action plan 2013-2020 was adopted by the 66th World Health Assembly, described by the Director-General, as a landmark achievement focusing international attention on a long-neglected problem rooted firmly in the principles of human rights (WHO, 2019). The action plan aims to strengthen effective leadership and governance for mental health; provide comprehensive, integrated and responsive mental health and social care services in community-based settings; implement strategies for promotion and prevention in mental health; and strengthen information systems, evidence and research for mental health. It calls for a change in the attitudes that perpetuate stigma and discrimination that have isolated people since ancient times, and it calls for an expansion of services in order to promote greater

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efficiency in the use of resources. The UN General Assembly formulated the Sustainable Development Agenda to transform the world by 2030 by promoting mental health and well-being, and the prevention and treatment of substance abuse (United Nations General Assembly on 25 September 2015). For translating such resolutions into practice, “Think globally but act locally” is a relevant statement for assessing the status of mental health in indigenous populations such as Nagaland and the rest of northeast region of India focusing in particular on the role of traditional healing practices. Hence this research on practices and perspectives on traditional healing in mental health that provides the data for the World Health Organisation (WHO) action plan and guidelines for further research. Gracey & King (2009) comment on the mental health action plan stating the determinants and disease patterns in indigenous populations. Albert & Kharkongor (2010) emphasize the need for building bridges between traditional and modern medicine for well-being through counselling and psychotherapy based on the studies of Khasi and Jaintia people of Northeast India. In a study on Latinos in the faith-based setting, Caplan (2019) describes the intersection of cultural and religious beliefs about mental health and mentions that stigma and cultural and religious values play a significant role in mental health care utilization disparities. Some indigenous groups, as they move from traditional to transitional and modern lifestyles, are rapidly acquiring lifestyle diseases, such as obesity, cardiovascular disease, and type 2 diabetes, and physical, social, and mental disorders linked to misuse of alcohol and of other drugs. Correction of these inequities needs increased awareness, political commitment, and recognition rather than governmental denial and neglect of these serious and complex problems. Nguyen et. al. (2019) report on the informal mental health interventions for people with severe mental illness in low and lower middle-income countries and recommend training and supportive supervision for informal community care providers as crucial components of effective interventions. In a case study of mental health in Uganda, Africa, a narrative analysis was done to link modern medicine and traditional medicine and identified several areas of convergence (Aboo et al, 2019). In a study on developing alliances to expand traditional indigenous healing practices within Alberta health services in Canada, Drost (2019) concludes that access to both traditional indigenous healing practices and western medicine are needed for all encompassing holistic health. Indigenous people should be encouraged, trained, and enabled to become increasingly involved in overcoming these challenges. In view of the wide popularity of traditional healing practices globally and particularly in indigenous populations, there is an urgent need to document and evaluate these practices as applied to healing of mental disorders. Dialogue formation between the formal and informal health workers is crucial in establishing trust and respect between both practitioners and in improving mental health care.

The WHO (2008) defines traditional medicine as “the sum total of the knowledge, skills, and practices based on the theories, beliefs, and experiences indigenous to different cultures, whether explicable or not, used in the maintenance of health as well as in the prevention, diagnosis, improvement or treatment of physical and mental illness”. Traditional medicine is an amorphous concept that comprises a range of

long-standing and still evolving practices based on diverse beliefs and theories (Bodeker & Burford, 2008). Within a given culture, elements of indigenous medicine knowledge may be diffusely known by many, or may be gathered and applied by those in a specific role of healer such as a shaman or midwife. Three factors legitimize the role of the healer – their own beliefs, the success of their actions and the beliefs of the community.

According to Helms & Cook, 1999 (as cited in Yeh, Hunter, Bahel, Chiang & Arora, 2004), the divergent worldviews of various cultures produce different concepts of mental health, physical well-being, and spirituality. They state that from the beginning of human existence, all cultural groups have developed not only their own explanations of abnormal behaviors, but also culture-specific ways of dealing with human problems and distress.

Lee & Armstrong, 1995 (as cited in Yeh et al, 2004) talks about another aspect of healing which, in many cultures, is a reality that is referred to as the “realm of spirits” and it is here that human destiny is often decided. For many helpers in this tradition, the goal is to enter this realm, in some fashion, on behalf of other people and the helpers then act as conduits of positive energy from this dimension. This energy is then translated into concrete insights or action leading to problem resolution or decision making.

Nagaland is one of the states of North Eastern India which is bordered in the East by Myanmar, Assam in the West Manipur in the South and Arunachal Pradesh and partly Assam in the North. It is extremely rich in biodiversity with several studies conducted on traditional medicine (Deorani & Sharma, 2007; Jamir & Upadhyay, 1998; Sangtam et al, 2012). Numerous ethno botanical plants have been identified which are a source of traditional medicine and traditional methods of healing practices (Jamir et al, 2012; Medhiet al, 2013). Other prevailing healing practices include divination, bone setting and zoo-therapy (Kakati & Doulo, 2002; Tetso, 2008).

Various studies have confirmed that traditional medicine is still popular and usually resorted to as the first step in the treatment of any diseases before seeking other systems of medicine (Saha et al, 2014). This may be truer in the case of mental ill-health but there is scant literature published. In a study by Thirthalli et al (2016), it was reported that no studies from India could be identified that investigated systematically the proportion of people with mental illness in the community who sought the services of traditional medicine. The preference for traditional medicine seems more prevalent in the northeast region of India (Govt. of India, 2012). Coincidentally, the health scenario in the northeast India is the poorest and many of the common health indicators are ranked lowest in various northeastern states (Govt. of India, 2015). If the health of the population in northeastern states has to improve, it is urgent that an objective and comprehensive assessment be made on the practice of traditional folk medicines as compared to the allopathic medicine widely promoted in the government primary health system.

Mental disorders can be narrowly defined as “evil/ demon” possession requiring supernatural intervention or broadly defined as abnormal or deviant behavior, various psychosis and neurosis, depression, anxiety, stress and similar distresses. Given the

scarcity of qualified psychologists and psychiatrists in most poor resource countries especially in indigenous populations, various local practitioners have taken over the role of experts in managing mental disorders. The outcomes of many of the interventions are unknown. With the advent of Christianity and Buddhism, many ancient religions have revived age-old practices to treat mental disorders, but there are no systematic studies on these aspects. Indigenous populations generally suffer from the triple problems of poverty, illiteracy and superstition which magnify even simple ailments and common mental disorders. There is an urgent need to therefore identify the burden of mental illness and the role of traditional healing practices in such communities.

Today, in Nagaland, there is only one Mental Hospital in the state capital Kohima now renamed as the State Mental Health Institute headed by one Senior Medical Officer and one Medical Officer (Department of Health and Family Welfare, n.d). In the article, "Talking about mental illness, the first step" (2017), it was reported in Morung express that Nagaland also has only six in-service psychiatrists with some posted as medical officers of government health centers and only two districts are covered under the Mental Health Programme. The scenario being such, the question arises as to how the Naga tribal population goes about addressing these and if traditional treatments are being made used of and how traditional healers play a role in the delivery of mental health care, their accessibility, acceptability and effectiveness. Published scientific literature on these aspects is scarce. Several urgent research questions are relevant and necessary to move forward such as whether traditional healing practices for mental health are popular among the Naga population, and what is the help-seeking behaviour of the Naga population in using traditional healing practices for mental health in terms of accessibility, satisfaction and outcomes, etc. These unanswered questions were addressed through a major research project during 2017- 2018 to describe the use of traditional healing practices for mental disorders among the Naga population and their associations with gender, tribes, urbanization, literacy and other socioeconomic factors as well as type and severity of mental disorder. Attitudes, perspectives and scope of future needs and demands were also ascertained.

Material and Methods

Assuming a prevalence of all mental disorders as 20%, and assuming that at least 60% would seek traditional healing at some stage of the disease, with a type 1 error of 5%, power of 80%, and a precision of 20%, the minimum sample size to be studied was decided as 700-800 persons. This was proportionately divided as around 500 rural and 300 urban. In consultation with state and district officials and experts, one urban district Dimapur and Two rural districts Mokokchung in the north-west and Kiphire in the south-east were chosen from which multi-stage representative random cluster samples of households were selected. The map of Nagaland is shown in Figure I.

The researcher first met the village heads and ward chairmen to introduce the project and established good rapport and got their permission to carry out the study with the residents of their respective villages and wards. The research topic, being of a very sensitive nature and the stigma associated with mental disorders, proved to be

quite a challenge. The household interview schedule was divided into four parts based on the research objectives: the first part was developed to gather information on attitudes to and utilization of traditional medicine during the past one year for general health problems, age and sex of the patient, treatment given, if it was effective, whether supplemented by any other therapy and if they would seek traditional medicine for the same problem and why. The second part made enquiries on knowledge of any mental disorders and if they think they were common in Nagaland. The third part was developed to gather information on any mental health problems in the family during the past one to five years, age and sex, when it started, their perception of the underlying cause, if they sought help from a traditional healer, treatment given and the outcome. The fourth part made enquiries on the overall satisfaction of traditional healers for both general and mental health, if they would recommend other people to seek traditional healing for mental health problems, if traditional healing was still popular for both general and mental health, reasons for it, if traditional healers needed additional training and also any traditional remedies kept at home. In order to examine similarities and carry out sub-analyses according to the objectives, information was collected on a variety of demographic variables including age, gender, tribe, religion, occupation, marital status, number of family members living with him/her, number of children living with him/her and type of family. Interview schedules were subjected to pilot studies for validation of the tools and feasibility and also to ensure that the tools were non-threatening.

All data gathering tools were made computerizable for data entry onto Microsoft Excel sheets and analysed using SPSS. Since the lay person's diagnosis of the illness was usually symptomatic and voluminous, efforts were made to condense them into a standard internationally acceptable format, and after discussion with experts, the ICD 10 classification for mental disorders was used. The traditional methods of healing included herbal preparations, manual or mechanical methods of therapy such as massaging, varieties of divinations and exorcism, use of rituals using zoo-therapy, trances, etc., and required grouping into broad categories. Questions dealing with outcomes or effectiveness, recommendations or popularity and other perspectives tended to be subjective but had to be summarised before entry on the excel sheets. Data which could not be reduced to tabulated form are presented by way of narratives. House-to-house visits were conducted wherein only adult respondents (more than 15 years of age) were included in this study who were interviewed in-depth and took approximately 45 minutes per household.

Findings

The distribution of respondents by age in the rural and urban samples are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of respondents by age and area

Age (years)	Rural		Urban		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Below 30	154	30.2	108	36.0	262	32.2
30-49	229	44.9	128	42.7	357	44.1
50 & above	127	24.9	64	21.3	191	23.5
Total	510	100.0	300	100.0	810	100.0

In both the rural and urban areas, half of the respondents were middle aged (44.9%, 42.7%), 30.2% in rural and 36.0% in urban were young adults and 24.9% in rural and 21.3% in urban were elderly. In 810 households, 59.9% of the respondents were females as compared to 40.1 % of male respondents. In the rural area, the households comprised of four tribes: Ao (21.6%), Sumi (29.4%), Yimjunger (19.6%) and Sangtam (29.4%). In the urban block the households belonged to different tribal groups, majority belonging to Ao tribe (40.0%).

Almost all the respondents were Christians in both the rural (100.0%) and urban areas (96.0%) except for a few belonging to Hindu, Muslim and other religion in the urban area. In the rural area, most of the respondents (31.4%) had no formal education, 33.3% had studied up to primary school, 25.5% had studied up to middle school and the few remaining (9.8%) up to high school. Whereas, in the urban block, only few (0.7%) were illiterates with no formal education with the majority of the respondents having formal education. Most of the respondents were either unemployed, homemakers and students in both the rural (51.0%) and urban areas (45.5%). How

ever, in the rural area a large number of respondents (29.4%) were also agricultural labourers whereas in the urban area 20.7 % had white collar jobs, were teachers and lawyers. Majority of the respondents in both the areas were married (20.9%, 53.3%). Only few were widowed in both the rural and urban areas (2.7%, 5.7%) and the remaining either divorced/separated (1.8%, 1.3%). In both the rural and urban areas, almost all households (96.0%, 89.8%) belonged to nuclear type of families. Only few belonged to joint families (10.2%, 4.0%). Traditional Modes of healing Mental disorders: Three main modalities of treatment were used by the traditional healers either singularly or in combination for managing mental disorders. These are Herbal (Ethno-botanical), Mechanical and Psycho-spiritual. Examples of these 3 methods are described in Tables 2,3 and 4.

Table 2: Common ethno-botanical (herbal) treatments

Sl. no	Description
1	Tsungrempang moli/ mozü (Cyclea peltata, Hook.f and Thunb), leaves crushed and consumed or used as a herbal bath.
2	Nangpera (Ocimum basilicum/Basil) leaves consumed.
3	Ao moli/ mozü (translated as Ao medicine) consists of a mixture of various herbs which has been sundried and pounded into a powder form.
4	Thangbu (rhus simialata, murr/nutgall tree), the fruit of which is sun-dried, pounded into a powder form.
5	Crushed neem (Azadirachta indica) leaves applied on the body
6	Mustard oil, crushed ginger & garlic

Table 3: Manual treatments

Sl. no	Description
1	Gently massaging nerves and joints.
2	For females, gently massaging the navel area.
3	Poking a needle onto the entire back area & biting onto the stomach area to suck out the impurities.
4	Rolling a local egg with a banana leaf and making a small opening on the top part of the egg. This is pressed on certain body parts to extract 'dirt', 'poison', 'curse'.
5	Placing a piece of rolled paper smeared with mustard oil on the navel and burning the top portion.

Table .4: Psycho-spiritual treatments

Sl. no	Description
1	The diviner travels to the Land of the Dead in his/her dream, called Asühläng, in search of the person's soul, believed to have been taken away by the spirits of departed relations or ancestor spirits.
2	Instructs to sprinkle water around the bed before bedtime and to place a bowl of water under the bed for three consecutive nights.
3	To refrain from eating meat and not letting in any visitors inside the house.
4	Sacrificing a rooster and offering rice and chilies to the malevolent spirits.
5	Instructs to place the deceased person's shawl under the pillow while sleeping at night.
6	Burns the person's clothes, rubs nangpera (<i>Ocimum basilicum</i> /Basil) all over the body, bathes the person daily with warm water and places a bowl of water near the bed every night.
7	A small branch of a peach tree is split into six similar pieces with the use of a dao, a traditional machete. The healer flings pairs of it on the floor and by the direction in which it falls, the healer diagnoses the ailment and gives the instruction for treatment.
8	Putting pieces of straws of hay and pebbles in a cup of water and placing it under the bed before sleeping. On the fourth morning, the cup of water along with the hay and pebbles are thrown in the direction of the sunset.

Prevalence of mental disorders

Overall, 383 out of 810 households (47.3%; 95% C I:43.9 - 50.7) reported some mental disorder in the past. 256 of 510 rural households (50.2%) as compared to 127 out of 300 urban households (42.3%), the difference statistically significant ($p < .05$). The mental disorders reported by the rural and urban samples using ICD-10 coding are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Mental disorders reported in rural and urban households

Mental Disorders	Rural No. (%)	Urban No. (%)	Total No. (%)	Rural-Urban difference p
Organic mental disorders	38 (14.8)	6 (4.7)	44 (11.5)	<0.001
Disorders due to psychoactive substance use	37 (14.5)	9 (7.1)	46 (12.0)	<0.001
Schizophrenia & related disorders	16 (6.2)	2 (1.6)	18 (4.7)	<0.01
Mood [affective] disorders	92 (35.9)	55 (43.3)	147 (38.4)	<0.05
Neurotic, stress-related and somatoform disorders	41(16.0)	47 (37.0)	88 (23.0)	.0001

Neurotic, stress-related and somatoform disorders	41(16.0)	47 (37.0)	88 (23.0)	.0001
Disorders of adult personality and behavior	13 (5.1)	4 (3.1)	17 (4.4)	NS
Behavioral syndromes	2 (0.8)	1 (0.8)	3 (0.8)	NS
Mental retardation	16 (6.2)	1 (0.8)	17 (4.4)	<0.01
Disorders of childhood and adolescence	1 (0.4)	2 (1.6)	3 (0.8)	NS
Total	256 (100.0)	127(100.0)	383(100.0)	

Overall, 38.4% reported mood disorders, 35.9% in the rural and 43.3% in the urban, the difference statistically significant($p<0.05$). In the rural area, nearly 15% also reported organic disorders, as compared to only 4.7% in the urban ($p <0.001$). On the other hand, nearly 40% reported neurotic, stress-related and somatoform disorders in the urban as compared to only 16% in the rural. ($p<0.001$.) Nearly 15% in the rural reported mental and behavioral disorders due to psychoactive substance use, mostly alcohol use, as compared to 7.1 % in the urban ($p<0.01$). In summary, as seen from the above table, organic mental disorders were significantly higher in rural area as compared to urban, while neurotic, stress-related and somatoform disorders were significantly higher in urban as compared to rural.

Consulting traditional healer

The number of households who sought help from a traditional healer for mental disorders is displayed in Table 6.

Table 6: No. of households who consulted a traditional healer in rural and urban samples

Consulted traditional healer	Rural	No. %	Urban	No. %	Total	No. %
Yes	89	34.8	21	16.5	110	28.8
No	167	65.2	106	83.5	273	71.2
Total	256	100.0	127	100.0	383	100.0

Nearly 30% (28.8%; 95% CI:23.8-33.8) consulted a traditional healer 34.8% in the rural and 16.5% in the urban, the difference statistically is highly significant ($n<0.0001$).

Traditional treatment of mental health problems

The traditional treatments given for each mental disorder combining both rural and urban samples are summarized in Table 7

Table 7: Traditional treatment given for each mental disorder combining both rural and urban samples

Mental Disorder	Treatment										All No. %
	Herbal (H) No. %	Manual (M) No. %	Psycho-spiritual (PS) No. %	H & M No. %	PS & H No. %	PS & M No. %	PS & H & M No. %	No treatment given			
Organic mental disorders	0 0.0	11 57.9	1 5.2	1 5.2	0 0.0	3 15.8	1 5.2	2 10.0			19 100.0
Disorders due to psychoactive substance use.	0 0.0	1 25.0	0 0.0	0 0.0	1 25.0	0 0.0	0 0.0	2 50.0			4 100.0
Schizophrenia, schizotypal and delusional disorders	1 8.3	1 8.3	9 75.0	0 0.0	0 0.0	0 0.0	1 8.3	0 0.0			12 100.0
Mood [affective] disorders	4 9.8	6 14.6	27 65.9	1 2.4	0 0.0	3 7.3	0 0.0	0 0.0			41 100.0
Neurotic, stress-related and somatoform disorders	3 13.6	2 9.1	12 54.5	2 9.1	0 0.0	2 9.1	1 4.5	0 0.0			22 100.0
Behavioural syndromes	0 0.0	1 11.1	5 55.6	2 22.2	1 11.1	0 0.0	0 0.0	0 0.0			9 100.0
Mental retardation	0 0.0	0 0.0	0 0.0	0 0.0	1 50.0	1 50.0	0 0.0	0 0.0			2 100.0
Disorders of childhood & adolescence	0 0.0	1 100.0	0 0.0	0 0.0	0 0.0	0 0.0	0 0.0	0 0.0			1 100.0
% Total	8 7.3	23 20.9	54 49.0	6 5.7	3 2.7	9 8.1	3 2.7	0 0.0			110 100.0

The traditional treatments for each mental disorder are presented for the rural area in Table 8 and for the urban samples in Table 9.

Table 8: Traditional treatment given for each mental disorder in rural samples

Mental Disorder	Treatment														
	Herbal (H)	Manual (M)	Psycho-spiritual (PS)	H & M	PS & H	PS & M	PS & H & M	No. %	No. %	No. %	All				
Organic mental disorder	0	11	1	1	0	3	0	0.0	0.0	17.6	0	1	5.8	17	100.0
Disorders due to psychoactive substance use	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0.0	50.0	0	0	0	0.0	2	100.0
Schizophrenia, schizotypal and delusional disorders	1	1	9	0	0	0	0	0.0	0.0	0	0	1	8.3	12	100.0
Mood [affective] disorders	1	3	27	0	0	3	0	0.0	0.0	8.8	0	0	0.0	33	100.0
Neurotic, stress-related and somatoform disorders	1	2	11	0	0	0	0	0.0	0.0	0	0	0	0.0	14	100.0
Behavioural syndromes	0	0	5	2	1	0	0	0.0	12.5	0	0	0	0.0	8	100.0
Mental retardation	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0.0	50.0	1	50.0	0	0.0	2	100.0
Total	3	18	53	3	3	7	0	3.4	3.4	8.0	0	0	0.0	89	100.0

Table 9: Traditional treatment given for each mental disorder in urban samples

Mental Disorder	Treatment										All No. %
	Herbal (H) No. %	Manual (M) No. %	Psycho- spiritual (PS) No. %	H & M No. %	PS & H No. %	PS & M No. %	PS & H+M No. %	No treatment given			
Organic mental disorders	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	50.0	2	100.0
Schizophrenia, schizotypal and delusional disorders	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	100.0	2	100.0
Mood [affective] disorders	3	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.0	7	100.0
Neurotic, stress-related and somatoform disorders	2	0	1	2	0	2	1	0	12.5	8	100.0
Behavioural syndromes	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0	1	100.0
Disorders of childhood & adulthood	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0	1	100.0
Total	5	5	1	3	0	2	3	2	9.6	21	100.0

The treatments given for each mental disorder combining both rural and urban samples reveal that mood disorders, mostly depression, which accounts for majority of the mental disorders for which traditional healers were consulted was mainly treated using psycho-spiritual form of healing (65.9%), manual treatment (14.6%) and herbal treatment (9.8%), a combination of psycho-spiritual and manual (7.3%) and a combination of herbal and manual (2.4%). For neurotic, stress-related and somatoform disorders too, psycho-spiritual form of treatment (54.5%) was the most common treatment given. The remaining few cases were treated using herbal (13.6%) and manual treatments (9.1%), a combination of herbal and manual (9.1%), a combination of psycho-spiritual and manual (9.1%) and a combination of all three modalities (4.5%). In contrast, most of the organic disorders such as Alzheimer's dementia and seizure disorders were treated using manual treatments (57.9%) with only one case being treated with psycho-spiritual form of treatment. The rest of the organic disorders were treated using a combination of psycho-spiritual and manual treatments (15.8%), a combination of herbal and manual (5.2%) and a combination of all three modalities (5.2%). Majority of the schizophrenia and related disorders were also treated through psycho-spiritual form of treatment (75.0%) with the remaining few treated through herbal (8.3%), manual (8.3%) and a combination of all three modalities of treatment (8.3%). Behavioural syndromes associated with physiological disturbances and physical factors such as nonorganic insomnia disorders and sleep terrors were treated also mostly treated with psycho-spiritual form of treatment, two cases were treated with a combination of herbal and manual treatments, one case with manual treatment and another case with a combination of psycho-spiritual and herbal treatments. Only two individuals with mental and behavioural disorders due to psychoactive substance use were given traditional treatment with one case treated with manual treatment and another with a combination of psycho-spiritual and herbal treatments. The other two cases were given no treatment. Two cases of mental retardation were also treated using a combination of psycho-spiritual and herbal and a combination of psycho-spiritual and manual.

In general, herbal treatments were statistically significantly higher ($p < 0.01$) in the urban as compared to rural (23.8 vs 3.4) while the psycho-spiritual treatments were statistically significantly higher ($p < 0.001$) in the rural as compared to urban (60.9 vs 4.8). On the other hand, the mechanical treatments were not statistically significantly different between urban and rural.

Outcome of traditional healing

Of those with mental health problems who were given traditional treatment, nearly 60% reported that the outcome was good resulting in great improvement in their condition. Only 35.2 % reported that the outcome was poor. More than half in both the rural and urban areas reported that the outcome was good. Only 36.4% in the rural and 30.0% in the urban reported that the outcome was poor. The differences between rural and urban were not statistically significant. Excellent or good satisfaction was mentioned by slightly over 50% of rural respondents but only 26% for urban but the differences barely reach statistical significance. On the other hand, rural householders

stated that traditional healing practice was unsuitable or not good for 32% of the illnesses, as compared to 43% in the urban. When asked if they would recommend traditional healing for mental disorders, nearly half in the rural but only a quarter in the urban said they would do so. The difference between rural and urban is highly significant ($p < 0.001$). The reasons given by the households for such recommendations are summarized in table 10.

Table 10: Reasons for recommendation of traditional healing for mental health

Area	Reason	No.	%
Rural	I have strong faith in traditional healing	51	21.4
	Able to offer effective treatment	65	27.3
	Depends on the severity of illness	8	3.4
	As a first step	23	9.7
	TH has diagnostic ability for mental disorders	12	5.0
	Capable of casting off evil spirits	6	2.5
	TH better when allopathy fails	23	9.7
	Witnessing other people getting healed	8	3.4
	More affordable	5	2.1
	TH more accessible and approachable	18	7.6
	TH has no side effects	5	2.1
	Some illnesses can be healed only by TH	10	4.2
	Seek all treatment options	4	1.7
Urban	I have strong faith in traditional healing	16	20.8
	TH better when allopathy fails	10	13.0
	Seek all treatment options	9	11.7
	Suitable for some illnesses	26	33.8
	Able to offer effective treatment	7	9.1
	TH has diagnostic ability for mental disorders	5	6.5
	Capable of casting off evil spirits	4	5.2

The main reasons for recommending traditional healing for mental health were their strong faith, belief that they can offer effective treatment and being suitable for some illnesses, if not all. Also they would recommend as a first step and believe that traditional healing is better when allopathy fails.

The reasons for not recommending traditional healing for mental health are summarized and presented in Table 11.

Table 11: Reasons for not recommending traditional healing for mental health

Area	Reason	No.	%
Rural	Modern medicine is better	36	13.2
	No faith in TH	18	6.6
	Faith only in Christian religious healing	15	5.5
	TH is ineffective	95	34.9
	Self coping skills is more important	3	1.1
	Unsuitable for some illnesses	81	29.8
	TH are uneducated, no formal training	5	1.8
	Seeking TH is against Christian beliefs	19	7.0
Urban	Faith in allopathy only	59	26.5
	Prefer prayer centers	15	6.7
	Seeking TH is against Christian beliefs	3	1.3
	Faith in God only	25	11.2
	TH is ineffective	12	5.4
	I have no faith in TH	61	27.4
	Seek only qualified counsellors and psychiatrists	16	7.2
	Prefer rehabilitation centers	2	0.9
	Unsuitable for some illnesses	13	5.8
	TH are uneducated, no formal training	17	7.6

The main reasons for not recommending were traditional healing being ineffective for mental health problems, not suitable for all illnesses, skepticism of traditional healing, faith in allopathy only and having complete faith in God alone. They also state that seeking help from traditional healers is against Christian beliefs, prefer Christian religious healing only and some would recommend only qualified mental health professionals and rehabilitation centres.

On enquiring if traditional healers are still popular for treating mental disorders, nearly 60% in the rural but only 24% in the urban felt that they were, the difference statistically significant ($p < 0.01$).

As stated for recommendation, the main reasons for mentioning that traditional healing were popular were their strong faith, belief that they have the diagnostic ability and because they adopt culturally acceptable methods. Also they affirm that traditional healing is better than allopathy in effectiveness, is more easily available, more affordable, more approachable and have power over spirits.

Only 11% of rural respondents felt that traditional healers require any additional training as compared to 35% in the urban.

Analysis of consultation of traditional healer by mental disorder

The number of households that consulted a traditional healer by mental disorder is

given in Table 12.

Table 12: Consultation of traditional healer by mental disorder

Mental disorder	Consulted traditional healer				Total No	%
	Yes	%	No	%		
Organic, including symptomatic, mental disorder	18	40.9	26	59.1	44	100.0
Schizophrenia, schizotypal and delusional disorders	2	4.3	44	95.7	46	100.0
Mood [affective] disorders	14	77.8	4	22.2	18	100.0
Neurotic, stress-related and somatoform disorders	40	27.2	107	72.8	147	100.0
Behavioural syndromes associated with physiological disturbances & physical factors	24	27.3	61	69.3	88	100.0
Disorders of adult personality and behavior	9	52.9	8	47.1	17	100.0
Mental retardation	0	0.0	3	100.0	3	100.0
Behavioural & emotional disorders with onset usually occurring in childhood & adolescence	2	11.8	15	88.2	17	100.0
Mental and behavioural disorders due to psychoactive substance use	1	33.3	2	66.7	3	100.0
Total	110	28.8	273	71.2	383	100.0

For mental disorders such as organic disorders and behavioural syndromes associated with physiological disturbances & physical factors, about half of the households had sought traditional healing. Majority (77.8%) of the households with schizophrenia and related disorders had consulted a traditional healer; whereas of those households with mental retardation and substance use, only few chose to seek traditional healing (11.8%, 4.3%). Also, for households with mood disorders and neurotic, stress-related and somatoform disorder, only a small number (27.2%, 27.3%) had consulted a traditional healer. Nearly 78% of those who were treated using psycho-spiritual form of treatment reported that the outcome was good with only 17% stating that the outcome was poor. Herbal treatment seems to have had a positive outcome for half of those treated. In contrast, almost 75% of those treated using manual treatment reported that the outcome was poor.

Discussion

Mental disorders contribute significantly to the burden of disease across the globe and constitute a formidable challenge for health services (Alonso et al, 2013; Belfer, 2008; Charles et al, 2016; WHO, 2005; World Bank, 1993). Although the research was not an epidemiological study of mental disorders, a baseline was needed to pursue the follow up. In the light of such a high prevalence of mental health problems, 28.8% of

those with mental disorders had consulted a traditional healer in the present study (Table 6). It is quite possible that the low percentage in making use of traditional methods could be due to the decline in the number of traditional healers for mental health or that they are generally perceived as incapable of treating mental disorders (Table 11). Other reasons could also be that traditional healing is generally seen as ineffective or it could also be due to the stigma attached to consulting traditional healers after the advent of Christianity in the state and the popularity of Christian religious healers and prayer centres increasing in recent years (Table 11). On the other hand, those who had consulted might have had a preference for traditional healing which could mainly be due to a strong faith in the system and the use of culturally acceptable methods of healing by the traditional healers (Table 10).

In a study on help-seeking behaviour of patients with mental health problems visiting a tertiary care center in north India (Mishra et al, 2011) it was found that nearly one third of the patients had consulted a traditional faith healer at some point in the course of their illness. Another Indian study conducted in 2015 (Shidhaye & Vankar) in a tertiary care center in Western India found that 54.7% of the patients had consulted a traditional healer before going to the psychiatric hospital. What is noteworthy in the present study is the significant differences between the rural and urban householders with 34.8% in the rural but only 16.5% in the urban seeking traditional healing (Table 6). This indicates that the use of traditional methods for mental health is still quite popular especially in rural Nagaland, much less in the urban area but still popular at least as a first step. A similar case can be seen in Ghana (Appiah-Poku et al, 2004) whereby fewer patients with mental health problems present to traditional healers in modern, urban Africa compared to rural areas. In the present study, although the number of households who consulted a traditional healer is small, majority (58.5%) felt that the outcome was good. Given that most of the mental disorders for which traditional healers were consulted were mood disorders, mainly depression (37.2%) and neurotic, stress related and somatoform disorders (20.0%) for which psycho-spiritual form of intervention was most commonly used, it is possible that their faith in the system might have played a big role in the healing process (Table 10).

In terms of satisfaction of traditional healing for mental health, excellent or good satisfaction was mentioned by 25% for urban and slightly over 50% of rural respondents. Its also interesting to note that a quarter in the urban and nearly half in the rural would recommend traditional healing for mental disorders. Overall, 21.4% of the respondents stated that they had strong faith in traditional healing. Some were also of the view that traditional healers have diagnostic ability for mental disorders (Table 10). Dr Otsyula, 1973 (as cited in Ndeti, 2006) reported that patients went to hospital only to look for the cure of their illness, whereas they went to see traditional doctors for both the cure and also to find out the cause of their illness. In a study conducted by Ae-Ngibise et al in Ghana, Africa (2010) respondents indicated many reasons for the appeal of traditional and faith healers, including cultural perceptions of mental disorders, the psychosocial support afforded by such healers, as well as their availability, accessibility and affordability.

Again, 24% in the urban and nearly 60% in the rural felt that traditional healing for mental health is still popular in Nagaland. Besides strong faith in traditional heal-

ing, majority of the respondents felt that traditional healers have power over spirits. Similar responses were found from the studies of Champion & Bhugra (1998), Chadda et al (2001) and Mishra et al (2011) revealing people's attribution of supernatural causation of mental disorders. In a study by Longkumer & Borooah (2013) on knowledge and attitudes toward mental disorders among Nagas, it was reported that a considerable number of participants reported evil spirit possession as the cause of mental disorders and preferred seeking for divine intervention as a treatment mode.

Popularity of traditional healing in the present study is also attributed to culturally acceptable methods of healing. Dalal (2016) stresses on cultural compatibility and how indigenous treatments are rooted in the faith and beliefs of the local communities. He asserts that sharing the same culture, the healer and his/her healing practices are integral to the beliefs and practice of the local communities and that the explanatory system which a healer employs is mostly congruous with the thinking of the community to which he/she belongs. Healing also entails restoring equilibrium between the mundane and supernatural worlds where Gods, ancestors and evil spirits are all considered to be a part of the healing process. Different healing practices use different forms of sacred rituals (not religious) and certain rituals are part of the complete cure of the person (Dalal, 2016). Kleinman, 1980 (as cited in Dalal, 2016) notes that prevalent socio-spiritual beliefs, rituals and practices create the necessary conditions for fostering a positive mental state of hope, optimism and initiative and that they serve as important inner resources to combat illness and other related adversities, and thereby enhance the efficacy of indigenous medicine. Dalal (2006) also dwells on the question of how such community beliefs which are considered as false and delusional by the scientific community and are attributed to superstition, illiteracy and ignorance may actually play a positive role in the recovery process and in adjusting to adverse life conditions. He questions how belief in God and supernatural can be tested or how one's faith in some person or group can be subjected to verification and reasons that faith and beliefs are often deep rooted, forming the basis of one's relation with self, family and community.

Despite the significant toll of mental illness on the Indian population, resources for patients often are scarce, especially in rural areas. Traditional healing has a long history in India and is still widely used, including for mental illnesses. However, its use has rarely been studied systematically as stated by Thirthalli et al (2016) who reported that no studies from India could be identified that investigated systematically the proportion of people with mental illness in the community who sought the services of traditional medicine. In a study of perceptions of traditional healing for mental illness in rural Gujarat (Schoonover et al, 2014), it was reported that subjects were largely dissatisfied with their experiences with traditional healers, but such healing was still an incredibly common first-line practice in Gujarat. They stated that because healers are such integral parts of their communities and so commonly sought out, collaboration between faith healers and medical practitioners would hold significant promise as a means to benefit patients. This partnership could improve access to care and decrease the burden of mental illness experienced by patients and their communities.

Decentralization of health services has been promoted and primary care services have been identified as playing the vanguard role in providing mental health care (WHO, 2003; Tol et al, 2011). In developing countries resources are limited, as are the skills and knowledge of primary care personnel (Azale et al, 2016; Demyttenaere et al, 2004; Kohn et al, 2004; Peterson et al, 2009; Saxena et al 2007). Hence, people engage in different pathways to psychiatric care (Poku et al 2001). This can be seen in Poland (Pawlowshi & Kiejna, 2004), in Singapore (Chong, et al 2005), in Eastern Europe (Richard et al, 2005; Gater et al 2005), in Bali (Kurihara, et al 2006), in Karachi (Naqvi & Khan, 2006) as well as in Australia (Steel et al, 2006). Uganda is no exception to this (Ovuga et al, 1999). This paper reports on a survey of such traditional healers in one area of Uganda. A significant proportion of people seek care from traditional and spiritual healers whom they consult for a range of medical problems. A Nigerian study also noted that spiritual healers, traditional healers and general practitioners were the first to be contacted by 13%, 19% and 47% of patients respectively (Gureje et al, 1995). In a study to investigate patterns of treatment seeking behavior and associated factors for mental illness in Southwest Ethiopia (Girmal & Tisfaye, 2011), it was found that half of the patients sought traditional treatment from either a religious healer 116 (30.2%) or an herbalist 77 (20.1%) before they came to the hospital. The most common explanations given for the cause of the mental illness were spiritual possession 198 (51.6%) and evil eye 61 (15.9%), whereas 73(19.0%) of the respondents said they did not know the cause of mental illnesses. The researchers report that there is significant delay in modern psychiatric treatment seeking in the majority of the cases since traditional healers were the first place where help was sought for mental illness.

Many consider traditional medicine to be unsystematic and not based on science, with voluminous apprehensions (Pal et al, 2015). Yet, due to reasons better known to them as care-seekers daily patronize traditional healers by accepting them as 'Friend, Philosopher and Guide'. Otherwise in absence of 'receivers of treatment' these traditional healers would not have survived over years with respect from the community. From the age old concept of 'Doctor' as 'healer, preacher and teacher', we have currently reached the era of evidence based medicine- 'What is the evidence that what you have just advised, works'. Practicing evidence based medicine will identify and apply the most efficacious interventions with ideas and concepts to think positively to maximize the chances of individuals, groups and communities to attain and sustain, long happy and fulfilled lives.

Otsyula, 1973 (as cited in Ndetei, 2006) further notes that several studies have suggested that many cultures have names for various mental health disorders, implying that they have long recognised them (Otsyula, 1973). The types of management prescribed by these traditional healers (often concurrently) fall into several main groups. These include the use of herbal preparations (pharmacotherapy) and several types of psychotherapy.

The WHO Traditional Medicine Strategy 2014-2023 will help health care leaders to develop solutions that contribute to a broader vision of improved health and patient autonomy. The strategy has two key goals: to support Member States in harnessing the potential contribution of T&CM to health, wellness and people-centred

health care and to promote the safe and effective use of T&CM through the regulation of products, practices and practitioners. These goals will be reached by implementing three strategic objectives: 1) building the knowledge base and formulating national policies; 2) strengthening safety, quality and effectiveness through regulation; and, 3) promoting universal health coverage by integrating T&CM services and self-health care into national health systems.

As mentioned earlier, the findings from this research highlight the continuing popularity and preferences to seek traditional healing for alleviating mental health problems in Nagaland. The reasons for their popularity emphasizes the acceptable methodology followed by the traditional healers based on local culture, approachability and good rapport.

Thus far, this is the largest study in Nagaland that should provide leads for meaningful action programs to benefit the people of Nagaland as well as provide possible leads for further research. A limitation of this study would perhaps be the evaluation of the effectiveness of traditional healing which was based solely on the personal opinion of the respondents.

More qualitative research in terms of specific case reports and ethnographic studies as well as biographical and professional sketches of the traditional healers would also provide better guidance on integrating traditional healing practices with modern psychiatric care and contemporary counselling programs for the people of Nagaland. Serious efforts must continue to integrate and chose the best in traditional and modern mental health care, so that we do not make the mistake of “throwing the baby with the bath water”. Nagaland offers a unique opportunity to integrate the best traditional healing practices into formalized counselling and psychotherapy programs. Further research could focus on in-depth interview surveys on more traditional healers from different parts of Nagaland and combining this survey with qualitative approaches such as focus group discussions to develop linkages and bridges between traditional healing and modern psychiatric care.

Conclusions

Traditional healing practices are widely followed more for general sicknesses than for mental disorders. For a majority of people in Nagaland, traditional methods of healing mental disorders still remain the first point of contact and pursued till the problem is alleviated. There are significant rural urban differences with less urban population resorting to traditional methods. The main modalities of traditional healing are the use of ethno-botanical or herbal concoctions, manual methods such as massaging, performing psycho-spiritual rituals and procedures, and occasionally ethno-zoological remedies. Mood disorders were the predominant mental health problem and in a majority of cases, psycho-spiritual therapies were administered. The outcome of traditional treatments for mental health problems is mostly positive, with more than half of those who used traditional healing reporting that there was a change in their condition. There are significant rural urban differences with regard to satisfaction of traditional methods for mental health problems.

It is concluded that integration of traditional healing with modern allopathic

psychiatric practices will significant benefit the Nagaland population and appropriate counselling programs will be necessary.

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